

Annual Report

2020 – 2021

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1 Message from the Director

Last month we celebrated the 5th anniversary of ODISSEI. In 5 short years we have come a long way. We have grown from just 23 member organisations in 2016 to 42 today. We have created the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer for analysing highly sensitive data, provided rapid access to a world class, representative panel during the COVID-19 national lockdown, and provided access to high quality data to hundreds of researchers. We are proud of these and many other accomplishments.

Just over a year has passed since we started the ODISSEI Roadmap project, and all tasks are now up and running and operating well to develop the ODISSEI infrastructure further. In addition to these tasks, ODISSEI is also collaborating closely with many successful projects from the Platform Digital Infrastructure - Social Science and Humanities (PDI-SSH). Work has also already begun on collaborations with other research infrastructures in other disciplines and other countries to build on our existing successes. These plans are indeed exciting, and we look forward to sharing them with you soon, but where the true excitement in ODISSEI currently lies is in the transition from planning to delivery.

This month we will have our first face to face event in two years when we host our annual Community Conference at the Muntgebouw in Utrecht. We have sorely missed intensive interaction with the ODISSEI research community, and we are keen to showcase the infrastructure that ODISSEI can provide them with. The next year is going to require the development and expansion of more structured information channels for researchers, like the community conference, so that they can navigate the myriad opportunities for accessing, linking, and analysing new data.

To achieve this, we have several initiatives planned over the next year. Next summer we will host the first ODISSEI Summer School for Computational Social Science which will provide early career researchers with an immersive series of workshops on using the ODISSEI infrastructure. We will also be scaling up the work of our Social Data Science Team who have recently hired several great young talents with an eclectic set of expertise. They will be engaging with researchers across the ODISSEI member organizations. We will also deliver the first iterations of the ODISSEI portal which will help researchers navigate the vast range of data that is available through ODISSEI.

The next year will therefore be focused on delivering on the promise of ODISSEI and ensuring that all researchers can benefit from its services. After 5 years of intensive development, for me this is where the exciting work can truly begin

Pearl Dykstra
Scientific director, ODISSEI

2 The Structure of ODISSEI

The ODISSEI acronym stands for Open Data Infrastructure for Social Science and Economic Innovations. At present, ODISSEI is made up of 42 [member organisations](#) and 1 observer member that financially contribute to its development. These member organisations include Social Science Faculties, Economics Faculties, Research Institutes, Public Research Agencies, Statistics Netherlands, and E-Infrastructure providers. The 43 organisations in ODISSEI represent more than 5,000 social science researchers and ODISSEI aims to support their research by providing world class data infrastructure services that increase their access to data, computing tools, expertise, and financial resources.

The [Supervisory Board](#) is elected by the member organisations to represent their interests and oversee the development of ODISSEI. In turn the Supervisory Board appoints the [Management Board](#) of ODISSEI with overseeing ODISSEI's programme of work. This programme of work was set out in the ODISSEI Roadmap application which has a budget of € 13.9 million and runs through to the end of 2024. Reviewers described the project as 'the envy of social scientists everywhere' and '*world leading*'. The implementation of the work programme is the responsibility of 15 partners, all of whom are ODISSEI member organisations. These 15 partners are coordinated by the [Coordination Team](#) at Erasmus University Rotterdam as the host participant of ODISSEI.

The programme of work is subdivided into four work streams which represent four separate ways in which ODISSEI serves the research community. First, the **Data Facility** ensures that researchers can find, access, and link the data that they need. At the centre of this work is the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer which allows researchers to analyse complex and rich data from Statistics Netherlands and other ODISSEI data providers in a secure, yet computationally powerful environment. ODISSEI also provides grants and support to access this data to facilitate new research.

The **Observatory** supports and maintains key long-standing data collection efforts and participation in the international social science data collections to which the Ministry of Education and Culture has committed itself (via so-called ERICs, European Research Infrastructure Consortiums). These include such studies as the European Social Survey, the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe and the Generations and Gender Programme. It also covers the Dutch Election Study which has been collecting data since 1971. This work stream is focused on providing a consistent, stable, and reliable stream of data for social scientists that could then be utilised across the infrastructure.

The **Laboratory** is where researchers can conduct their own experiments, primarily through the LISS Panel, operated by Centerdata. ODISSEI provides financing for the core LISS Panel but also provides access to researchers from ODISSEI member organisations to field their own questions to the LISS panel's representative and high-quality sample of over 4,500 households. The Laboratory is also where future ODISSEI upgrades and enhancements are developed and prototyped.

Finally, the **Hub** is where researchers are provided with support, expertise, and guidance in the use of ODISSEI services and facilities. It includes an educational programme, community events, remote access grants, data stewardship, as well as a Social Data Analytics Team at Utrecht University who can provide high quality and intensive support to researchers looking to deploy computational and data science methods within ODISSEI.

As a community, ODISSEI not only delivers services but also develops and promotes standards and best practices for social science research. ODISSEI not only promotes the FAIR principles through the delivery of new search and access services, but also by requiring adherence to FAIR from ODISSEI users. ODISSEI requires its users to act in accordance with the **principles of responsible data science**: Fair, Accurate, Confidential and Transparent (FACT). ODISSEI also supports open science by facilitating inclusion, sharing, and equity through its work. These principles are set out in the ODISSEI User Policy which was launched in Spring 2021.

3 Activities

In 2020-2021, ODISSEI conducted activities across the four work streams as defined in the ODISSEI Roadmap proposal. This section details those activities and the work that has been conducted at the time of reporting.

3.1 The Data Facility

3.1.1 Statistics Netherlands Microdata Access

ODISSEI stimulates the use of the rich microdata at Statistics Netherlands, particularly amongst early career researchers and first-time users. These pseudonymised microdata are available at the level of individuals, companies, and addresses. The data are made available to researchers in the secure Statistics Netherlands environment under strict conditions for statistical research, and can be combined with researchers' own datasets. However, the costs for obtaining access to these data can be prohibitive, especially for early-career researchers.

In early 2021, ODISSEI launched its annual call to facilitate access to microdata from Statistics Netherlands free of charge for researchers at ODISSEI member organisations (so-called **Microdata Access Grants**, MAG). The submission deadline was 30 April 2021. There were 26 applications to this call, which is a 50% increase on the year before. In June, six projects of ODISSEI member organisations were awarded an ODISSEI Microdata Access Grant (Table 1). The total value of the awarded projects is € 32,229. The amounts awarded are small, but the impact of access is large as they bring a new generation of researchers into contact with complex and sensitive administrative data and these projects would not have been possible without them.

The proposals were assessed by an independent, interdisciplinary committee consisting of Jan Kabatek (University of Melbourne), Paulina Pankowska (Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam), Katya Ivanova (Tilburg University), Erik-Jan van Kesteren (Utrecht University), and Marco Helbich (Utrecht University). Committee members were excluded from evaluating proposals with which they expressed to have some kind of connection. Each proposal was evaluated by three committee members. The committee then approved the final ranking of proposals.

ODISSEI also continued the **Microdata Access Discount** (MAD) in collaboration with Statistics Netherlands. From July 2020 to June 2021, ODISSEI provided a discount of up to 50% to 134 Statistics Netherlands microdata projects from ODISSEI member organisations. The topics are immensely diverse, covering crime, health sciences, demography, environmental issues, and genetics to name a few. The total value of these discounts was € 295,507. A full list of projects to have received the discount is available in Annex 1. Member organisations are however prohibited from claiming more than double their annual contributions.

Statistics Netherlands and ODISSEI are also investigating how the research community can best be served. Results are expected in the Winter of 2021.

Table 1 - Microdata Access Grant Awardees 2020-2021

Applicant	Affiliation	Project Title
Rob Timans	TiU-TSB	Private equity investment in the Netherlands: Who benefits?
Kim Fairley	UL-Law	Parental transition and healthy lifestyle choices
Bastian Ravesteijn	EUR-ESE	Using big data to give children a promising start in life
Gabriele Mari	EUR-ESSB	Less for more? Family size, child allowances, and child outcomes: Evidence from a Dutch reform
Linde Kattenberg	UM-SBE	The efficacy of energy efficiency: Home insulation and residential gas use
Sjoerd van Alten	VU-SBE	Genetic and environmental determinants of socioeconomic status in the Lifelines cohort

Coordination Team Contact: Kasia Karpinska (kasia@odissei-data.nl)

3.1.2 ODISSEI Use Cases

The Coordination Team cultivates a range of data products that are available for reuse within the Statistics Netherlands remote access environment and in the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer. Several projects have produced results that form the basis of further results including geo-spatial maps of the Netherlands which provide rich contextual information to individual records and network files which represent pseudonymised individuals as embedded within their networks. For example, since August 2020 Statistics Netherlands and the ODISSEI Coordination Team have been working on the development and documentation of a [whole population network](#) file that is now available to authorised users within the Statistics Netherlands secure remote access environment. Further data products will be added to the environment through the course of the project. The Coordination team has also launched an ODISSEI User Policy designed at making all outputs from ODISSEI projects FAIR, including those from the secure environments at Statistics Netherlands and the OSSC. These efforts are currently being extended, by providing specific workflows and platforms to deposit code.

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RESEARCH IMPACT

From Financial Crisis to Mental Health Crisis

Daniel Karpati, a PhD student at the University of Tilburg, linked data on firms' financial performance during the financial crisis of 2008 with their employee's usage of anti-depressants. He used this innovatively linked data to show that employees at firms most exposed to the financial crisis increased their use of anti-depressants even when compared to those who lost their job during this time. This demonstrates the ability of innovative data linkages to bridge disciplines as diverse as corporate finance and mental health.

Karpati, Daniel and Renneboog, Luc, Corporate Financial Frictions and Employee Mental Health (August 17, 2021). CentER Discussion Paper Nr. 2021-003, European Corporate Governance Institute – Finance Working Paper No. 796/2021, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3772659> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3772659>

3.1.3 ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer

Statistics Netherlands and SURF delivered an operational version of the **ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer** (OSSC) in September 2020. This facility is a global first enabling the analysis of highly sensitive administrative data that is linked to data from social surveys and other sources in a secure HPC environment. In autumn 2021, the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer was migrated to the new national supercomputer named Snellius. The ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer provides the fastest computing capacity in the Netherlands via the national supercomputer and obeys the highest standards for data protection both legally and technically, imposed by both Statistics Netherlands Law and Europe's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). It provides Statistics Netherlands' secure remote-access environment that can incorporate datasets and advanced analytics tools at the national supercomputer of SURF. Datasets include pseudonymised administrative microdata on persons, households, companies etc. from Statistics Netherlands as well as research data collected by ODISSEI members. Analysis of these highly secured datasets is possible due to the system's architecture: SURF acts as Trusted Third Party between the data provider and the researcher, and the analysis environment is strictly **controlled and protected**.

Development of the OSSC cost **€ 216,075** in 2020-2021 which was for SURF and Statistics Netherlands. This included adaptations to ensure the OSSC can service all member organisations. An acceleration in these investments is expected in 2021-2022 as the new OSSC environment on Snellius becomes operational. Since its formal launch, ODISSEI worked with 6 researchers in using the facility. Interest in the OSSC has been broad and for a diverse range of uses. Through 2022 the number of projects will be further increased and supported in their implementation and usage of OSSC with the Coordination Team monitoring progress.

Table 2 – Researchers currently executing research projects using the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer

Head researcher	Affiliation
Trond Husby	Planbureau voor de Leefomgeving (PBL)
Ana Petrović	TU Delft (TUD) - Faculty Architecture and the Built Environment
Maciek Strak	Rijksinstituut voor Volksgezondheid en Milieu (RIVM)
Jasper Selder	Amsterdam UMC
Joris Mulder	Centerdata
Elenna Dugundji	Centrum Wiskunde & Informatica (CWI)

Coordination Team Contact: Kasia Karpinska (kasia@odissei-data.nl)

3.1.4 ODISSEI Portal

The **ODISSEI Portal** promotes the reuse of existing datasets by making them Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR). Reusing existing datasets, rather than creating new ones, can result in lower costs (because data collection is not needed), a better data quality (because professional panels or register data carefully curate their data) and richer data (because professional panels and register data are inherently rich). By combining and linking datasets, new research questions can be addressed.

To facilitate FAIR use of data, the Portal will provide a variable level, searchable catalogue of data within ODISSEI member organisations. The Portal working group has been established and consists of representatives from DANS, VU, SURF and the ODISSEI Coordination team. The budget for this work in 2020-2021 was **€ 206,647**. In the past year, the team has made rapid progress towards a first iteration of the Portal which includes metadata from DANS, Centerdata and Statistics Netherlands. The incorporation of metadata from Statistics Netherlands is a significant milestone for ODISSEI and will ensure that Statistics Netherlands data becomes FAIR. This will help researchers who are applying to use LISS or Statistics Netherlands microdata through ODISSEI grants and access discounts in navigating the pre-existing data collections and rapidly identifying possible linkages and synergies between the data sources. In 2021-22, further data sources within the ODISSEI ecosystem will be added to extend the coverage and functionality of the Portal. Beta testing of the portal with an ODISSEI user group will be conducted in 2022.

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3.2 The Observatory

3.2.1 ODISSEI Data Collection Committee

ODISSEI finances Dutch participation in ERIC surveys and surveys of key strategic importance. In 2020-2021, ODISSEI provided financing for the Netherlands Election Study (**NKO - € 177,439**), the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (**SHARE - € 75,027**) and the European Social Survey (**ESS - € 45,000**). ODISSEI also paid the Dutch contribution for 2020 of the Luxembourg Income Study (**LIS - € 36,300**). To ensure that all fieldwork efforts within ODISSEI are efficient and that the resulting data can be fully integrated within ODISSEI, a **Data Collection Committee** is in place and includes four members: Marike Knoef (Chair), Gerbert Kraaykamp, Ineke Stoop, and Bella Struminskaya. In 2022 the committee will be overseeing the implementation of the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe and the Generations and Gender Survey. In addition to the data collection committee Marike Knoef supervises two data scouts at Leiden University who are responsible for identifying new datasets for use by ODISSEI member organisations and ensuring that they are FAIR. The work of the data scouts began in autumn 2021.

Coordination Team Contact: Tom Emery (tom@odissei-data.nl)

3.2.2 Media Content Analysis Lab

The Media Content Analysis Lab (MCAL) offers systematic analysis of large corpora of digital media content, where copyright and GDPR restrictions make it very hard to share media content data. A workbench is provided for researchers where they can share data and analyses with strict rights management, without the need to read or export the data themselves. Currently, several Dutch initiatives exist that facilitate retrieval, storage, and analysis of media content (i.e., the infrastructure for content analysis [INCA] at the University of Amsterdam and the Amsterdam Content Analysis Toolkit [AMCaT] at VU Amsterdam. Their use, however, requires considerable programming skills and existing initiatives are currently tailored to a limited set of applications. Through the Media Content Analysis Lab, the large amount of longitudinal media content data (i.e., online news data; social media data) currently available within ASCoR at University of Amsterdam will be made available to researchers at ODISSEI member organisations. It will also be possible to deposit new data, or to use specific tools on data stored elsewhere. The work on the Media Content Analysis Lab was initiated in June 2021 with the hiring of two postdocs at 0.5 FTE (**MCAL - € 10,032**) and through 2021-2022 the task will provide an inventory of media data to be integrated within ODISSEI, guidebooks for the exploitation of the tools used for content analysis and demonstrations of the interoperability of this data with other ODISSEI data providers.

Coordination Team Contact: Tom Emery (tom@odissei-data.nl)

3.2.3 Historical Sample of the Netherlands

The Historical Sample of the Netherlands (HSN) is currently linking the historical data file with the population registers held by Statistics Netherlands and enables links to be made between the birth

cohort of 1900-1922 with the administrative data held by Statistics Netherlands. The first iteration of linkage has been completed and led to 84% of the HSN being matched with records at Statistics Netherlands using secure, pseudonymized linkage. This will be iteratively improved over the coming months and the file will be made available for research purposes. The work is conducted by a team at the International Institute for Social History (IISG) and Statistics Netherlands, who started work in Spring 2021 (€ 21,268). This work forms a key bridge to the work conducted in CLARIAH that features in the 2022 Roadmap application.

Coordination Team Contact: Tom Emery (tom@odissei-data.nl)

3.2.4 Netherlands Twin Register

The Netherlands Twin Register (NTR) focuses on linking biomedical and cognitive data with the wider ODISSEI infrastructure through proof-of-concept projects within the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer and integrating the diverse metadata of NTR in the ODISSEI Portal. Work began in August 2021 and will form a key bridge to the work conducted in the [Consortium on Individual Development \(CID\)](#) and [BBMRI \(Netherlands Biobank Research Facility\)](#). Over the course of 2021-2022, the NTR team will develop a generic methodology for the Trust Third Party linkage conducted during their ODISSEI pilot and curate a standard and FAIR pedigree form dataset using data from within Statistics Netherlands. This file will be of wider use within Statistics Netherlands and will be extended using data from the HSN and other sources.

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RESEARCH IMPACT

Understanding the impact of COVID on the elderly

When the COVID pandemic struck and social distancing measures were introduced, social surveys were severely affected. Many social surveys are still collected face-to-face so that they can collect reliable health and wellbeing data, but the pandemic prevented this at precisely the time that such data was needed most. This was particularly the case for studies such as the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE) which focused on the elderly, a high-risk group. Through ODISSEI SHARE-NL was able to rapidly adapt and collect multiple waves of data via phone interviews throughout the pandemic. This data has been invaluable and provided keen insights into how the pandemic has affected the older population. For example, the data has been used to show that the pandemic has increased social inequalities in loneliness and depression, and this is particularly true for the oldest old.

Atzendorf, J. and Gruber, S., 2021. Depression and loneliness of older adults in Europe and Israel after the first wave of covid-19. European journal of ageing, pp.1-13.

3.3 The Laboratory

3.3.1 Distributed Analytics

The Distributed Analytics task is based around a primary use case involving the analysis of primary school students with special educational needs and is being developed in collaboration with Rolf van der Velden (Maastricht University). The distributed analytics system which has been developed by Michel Dumontier (also at Maastricht University) will allow researchers to run analysis on highly sensitive data without having access to such data. This approach is similar in design to the Personal Health Train and would greatly expand the type of data which could be included within ODISSEI. Because researchers never actually access the data, it allows for analytics to be run on data that was previously not accessible as the risk of disclosure is nullified. The initial phase of this project focused on the legal basis of processing this highly sensitive data and how it should be considered given the technical design. This work was conducted by the team at Maastricht University (€ 73,500). Once this phase is complete, the technical implementation can proceed in 2022.

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3.3.2 Automated Metadata Enrichment

Automated Metadata Enrichment is being led by Jacco van Ossenbruggen (VU). The social data within ODISSEI is highly structured and persistent identifiers and standardised codes are used pervasively. However, the degree of automated linkage is restricted by the lack of infrastructure that exists for such linkage. Computer science techniques are advancing using deep learning methods which help identify and link more opaque constructs within data that are less well defined and structured such as families, social networks, neighbourhoods, or even cultural groups. The potential of such techniques in the social sciences is considerable but these approaches require high levels of expertise. In this subtask, these high risk/high reward approaches are explored and examined to see if they can complement the more functional and established manual and semi-automated linkages which will be made in the development of the ODISSEI Portal. In 2020-2021 the team worked on a model for the standardization of data access licencing inherent within existing metadata across the portal to facilitate linkage (€ 33,962). In 2021-2022 this work will be extended to incorporate the metadata ingested from data providers such as Statistics Netherlands.

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3.3.3 The LISS Panel

The LISS panel, managed by Centerdata, consists of some 7,000 individuals from approximately 4,500 households. The panel is a representative sample of the adult population in the Netherlands. In 2020-2021, the panel was refreshed in order to maintain its representative nature and ensure that it is of sufficient quality for scientific research (€ 50,000). In June 2021, ODISSEI launched the fourth round of

the **LISS Grant**. This was the first time that applicants were also able to simultaneously apply for microdata access alongside their LISS data collection, allowing for the linkage of LISS data with the administrative data at Statistics Netherlands in a single project. The call for proposals closed on 23 September 2021. 27 proposals were submitted. 3 of these also requested access to Statistics Netherlands Microdata. Proposals are now being assessed by a committee of reviewers and successful applicants will be informed in Mid-December. The projects will commence from February 2021. The LISS Grants in the third round cost **€ 27,737** (up to and including June 2021).

In addition to LISS Grants, the **LISS panel** spent **€ 125,000** on its maintenance 2020-2021. Yearly fixed costs include personnel costs for panel management, subscription of broadband connection for panel members with initially no internet access, maintenance of hardware on loan to panel members, server and software license costs, and incentive costs for updating background variables and activation of 'sleeping' panel members (as to avoid attrition). Costs for the core study mainly consist of incentives for panel members, but also personnel costs for programming, testing, data cleaning and data dissemination. As a recognition to ODISSEI of the provided subsidy, Centerdata provided a 20% discount for using the LISS panel to projects from ODISSEI member organisations.

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3.3.4 Mass Experiments

The Mass Experiment Online Lab facilitates experiments in which large numbers of participants simultaneously interact under controlled conditions. These population-level experiments cannot be conducted in the traditional laboratory as they require scale in which network structure is systematically varied across multiple large-sized experimental populations (Centola, 2007; Bail, Merhout & Ding, 2018). The Mass Experiment Online Lab overcomes (1) the significant infrastructural and logistic challenges associated with simultaneous networked participation of many participants (Salganik, 2018) and (2) removes barriers-to-entry by providing methodological and organisational research facilities to interested but otherwise ill-equipped domain experts through a series of open calls. In 2020-2021 the Lab was piloted in an experiment on political polarization with a further use case to extend the functionality in early 2022 (**€ 8,821**). The development work has resulted in an extensive feasibility study which will be evaluated by the Management Board in Spring 2022 and has been used as the basis for further funding applications.

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3.3.5 Citizen Science

The ODISSEI Citizen Science Platform improves data quality in citizen science by applying existing expertise from the field of social science methodology. Citizen science projects include those which rely on ordinary citizens to collect scientific data at a large scale on for example air pollution, the backyard bird count, or the history of marriage. Underestimated aspects of data collection through citizen science

are issues of selectivity and measurement error. This platform performs three functions: (1) trusted and convenient data collection interface for fast development of Citizen Science applications through a web-based and mobile app platform to facilitate data collection; (2) link to spatial and demographic information from Statistics Netherlands to allow post-stratification to adjust for selectivity of the citizen scientist population and investigate the sensitivity of the conclusions; (3) double-coding and validation so researchers can estimate and correct for classification errors. The platform is built open-source and modular so that teams can easily add components to the study or change the look-and-feel. The Citizen Science task is led by Dr. Peter Lugtig at Utrecht University. Through 2020-2021 the Citizen Science team collaborated with the Social Data Analytics Team to create a range of tools to support citizen science, provide an inventory of citizen science projects in the Netherlands and develop a proposal for future funding to extend and develop the work (€ 77,000).

Coordination Team Contact: Kasia Karpinska (kasia@odissei-data.nl)

RESEARCH IMPACT

Are populists intolerant?

Dr. Linda Bos is an Assistant Professor at the University of Amsterdam and recipient of an ODISSEI LISS Grant. Using this grant, Dr. Bos and colleagues were able to collect data on levels of tolerance from a representative sample of the Dutch Population. Their analyses show that voters with stronger populist attitudes are less supportive of democratic norms, more intolerant of opposing views online, and of specific political opponents. The time on the panel and the quality of the sample allowed the team to design intricate instruments and examine the issue from multiple dimensions to ensure that the results were reliable and robust.

Bos, Linda, Lisanne Wichgers, and Joost van Spanje. "Are Populists Politically Intolerant? Citizens' Populist Attitudes and Tolerance of Various Political Antagonists." Political Studies (2021): 00323217211049299.

3.4 The Hub

3.4.1 Community Management

In 2020 the community conference was successfully held online with 149 participants and a specific focus on the work being done within ODISSEI in relation to the pandemic. The community conference in 2021 will be held at the Muntgebouw in Utrecht on Thursday 18th November 2021. The community managers are creating a program with a keynote session by Frank Pijpers (CBS & UvA) as well as sessions on innovative research projects in ODISSEI, Open Science with Sensitive Data, and on collaborations between the Social Science and Humanities.

The newsletter is currently being sent out to 596 individuals in either Dutch or English. The number of subscribers has increased by 55% and 41% open and read the email, which is very high for a newsletter of this kind. The two community managers are conducting ODISSEI showcase events over the coming months to increase the visibility and engagement of ODISSEI amongst practicing researchers within member organisations. They will explain all aspects of using ODISSEI to researchers. The community managers also run a wide range of events to engage the ODISSEI Community including task insight meetings for all people that are building ODISSEI, lunch lectures, and workshops¹. They operate the ODISSEI website and social media presence and contribute to the development of the E-data magazine.

The costs in this task also include the support for researchers using the ODISSEI infrastructure including the administration of all grant programs and assistance in using the range of facilities within ODISSEI. In autumn 2021, Angelica Maineri was appointed as a data manager to support researchers in the implementation of complex data management plans that are dependent on ODISSEI infrastructure and subject to the ODISSEI user policy. Community Management also entails the strategic development of ODISSEI through new grant applications, collaborations with other research infrastructures, and the secretarial functions in supporting the Supervisory Board, the Management Board, and all task leaders in the execution of their duties.

The Community Management costs were **€ 323,281** and included the costs of operating the entire Coordination Team.

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3.4.2 Educational Programme

The educational programme is currently being developed. In 2020-2021, events were largely held online which reduced the opportunities for effective educational engagement. In lieu, the new community managers are liaising with ODISSEI member organisations and graduate program officers to explore ways in which ODISSEI can foster greater coordination and fill perceived gaps in the educational resources and opportunities regarding computational social science. In 2021-2022, ODISSEI will host a

¹ <https://odissei-data.nl/calendar/>

Computational Social Science Summer School as well as several workshops hosted by ODISSEI service providers such as DANS, SURF, eScience Center, and Statistics Netherlands.

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3.4.3 ODISSEI Social Data Science Team

The ODISSEI Social Data Science Team (SoDa) was established in September 2020 and now contains six team members including Daniel Oberski (lead), Erik-Jan van Kesteren, Jonathan de Bruin, Parisa Zahedi, Shiva Nadi, and Javier Garcia-Bernardo. The costs in this task are all associated with staffing the team (€ 84,899). The ODISSEI Social Data Science team exists to support social scientists in their research projects. Researchers from ODISSEI member organisations can propose research projects for which computational, statistical, and research engineering skills will help answer questions which would otherwise remain unanswered. SoDa hosts a monthly Data Drop-in where researchers can ask all their questions surrounding data in social science and in their own research. Furthermore, SoDa cooperates with [ASReview](#) to support researchers who want to conduct systematic literature review with this tool. Projects supported by SoDa result not only in 'traditional' publications, but also in open-source reusable code that can be used for teaching purposes or as a starting point for other projects. The team has also supported many researchers in using other components of the infrastructure such as the OSSC, Microdata or LISS and coordinates with the eScience Center and the larger grants that they provide.

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3.4.4 Computational Social Science Grants

The Computational Social Science Grants are administered by the Netherlands eScience Center. The grants provide hours from eScience Research Engineers employed at the NLeSC to collaborate with social scientists to enhance their research, by exploiting digital technology. The grants are made available via an annual open call that is assessed by experts in the field of computational social science. The call for 2021 was opened in Spring 2021 and closed on 30th July 2021. A total of 7 applications were received and of these 5 were funded (See table below). As the awards were not made until the 4th quarter of 2021, the only costs for 2020-2021 are the initial administrative costs associated with establishing the first call (€ 1,874). In 2021-2022, the eScience Center intends to increase the visibility of the call and increase the number of applications received.

Table 3 – ODISSEI eScience Grants 2021

Researcher	Project
Andreas Flache	Interacting factors in school choice: modelling consequences for school segregation with an agent-based model
Irina Lock	The robot or the brain? Building a classifier for visual news frames of artificial intelligence
René Bekkers	Transparency in the Netherlands' non-profit sector
Farhad Mukhtarov	Markets for resilience or "disaster capitalism"? A multi-method critical discourse analysis of OECD's "Studies on Water" reports (2009-2021)
Javier Garcia-Bernardo	Tracking and visualizing states as fossil-fuel owners

Coordination Team Contact: Suze Zijlstra (suze@odissei-data.nl)

3.4.5 Benchmarking

In computational sciences, researchers often must choose between different computational approaches. Benchmarking uses standard datasets and parameters to systematically compare computational approaches and establish best practices in the community. Since translating research problems into benchmark studies is a novel concept in social sciences, workshops are organised on their design and to build consensus on the set-up for a specific task. This will eventually allow ODISSEI to monitor state-of-the-art algorithms for a specific task on the Enhance Your Research Alliance Benchmark Platform developed by NLeSC and SURF.

A large part of the astounding recent successes in machine learning have been ascribed to the application of the 'common task framework' (CTF), in which (1) a training dataset derived from ODISSEI infrastructure is publicly shared, (2) teams of experts compete for a common task pertaining to prediction on the training data, and (3) an impartial referee reports a performance score for each team based on held-out testing data. Fields in which this competition framework has been systematically applied, such as automated driving, machine translation, and medical imaging, have reported impressive and objectively quantifiable progress. Such benchmarks will allow social scientists to rapidly establish best practices in methodologies that are relatively novel in the field of social sciences. Actual work is expected to commence in early 2022.

The task moved from Netherlands eScience Center to VU Amsterdam-Faculty of Social Sciences.

Coordination Team Contact: Suze Zijlstra (suze@odissei-data.nl)

RESEARCH IMPACT

Using Agent Based Modelling to understand School Choice

Professor Andreas Flache was one of the recipients of the first round of ODISSEI Computational Social Science Grants. His project looks at school segregation, which is a persistent problem in the Dutch educational system. Interactions between and within individuals and schools are often not accounted for in existing research, but it is precisely these interactions that make school choice a complex system. It could lead to an incorrect understanding of the problem if the complexity of interactions is not modelled as such. Therefore, this project aims to model interactions explicitly in an Agent-Based Model (ABM) incorporating empirical data on multiple levels (e.g., households, schools, institutions) to study the consequences of interdependent, yet uncoordinated individual choices for the emergence of school segregation. This is an exceptionally complex task, and the project will require administrative data from Statistics Netherlands, the Secure Supercomputing Environment at SURF, and the assistance of research software engineers at eScience centre. Such projects are only now feasible with the infrastructure and technical expertise that ODISSEI provides.

4 Governance

ODISSEI now consists of **42 member organisations** and 1 observer member. In the last year, Centrum Wiskunde & Informatica (CWI) and De Nederlandsche Bank (DNB) joined the consortium. Almost all member organisations committed their financial contribution to ODISSEI until 2024, the end of the Roadmap project.

Through 2021, Amsterdam University Medical Center has been an observer member of ODISSEI. This means they contribute a membership fee and can use ODISSEI services but are not represented within the ODISSEI Supervisory Board. This is part of an assessment to ascertain the level of demand for ODISSEI services amongst **University Medical Centers** and the subsequent impact on ODISSEI operations. The results of this assessment will be given in Spring 2022.

The **Supervisory Board** now consists of Pieter Hooimeijer (DSW, chair), Carlo Schuengel (DSW), Henk van der Kolk (DSW), Arthur van Soest (DEB), Hanneke Imbens (Statistics Netherlands), Helga de Valk (KNAW/NWO institutes and E-infrastructures), and Sander Steijn (public research institutes).

The **Management Board** now consists of ten members: Pearl Dykstra (EUR, Chair and Director), Tom Emery (EUR, Deputy Director), Dorret Boomsma (VU), Tanja van der Lippe (UU), Marcel Das (Centerdata), Ruben Dood (Statistics Netherlands), Annette Langedijk (SURF), Henk Wals (DANS), Rob van Nieuwpoort (NLeSC), and Jacco van Ossenbruggen (VU). The Management Board meets monthly to discuss and evaluate the program of work.

The Coordination Team consists of six individuals: Tom Emery (Observatory Manager), Lucas van der Meer (Operational Manager), Kasia Karpinska (Scientific Manager), Angelica Maineri (Data Manager), Suze Zijlstra (Community Manager), and Godelieve de Wijer (Community Manager).

As part of the Roadmap Project, an **Advisory Board** has been established including Ron Dekker (CESSDA), Julia Lane (NYU), Melinda Mills (University of Oxford), Sally Wyatt (Maastricht University), and Amy O'Hara (Georgetown University). A virtual meeting took place in the Spring of 2021.

The 15 partners that execute the Roadmap project are Statistics Netherlands, Erasmus University Rotterdam, DANS, SURF, VU Amsterdam-Faculty of Science, NIDI, Leiden University-Faculty of Law, University of Amsterdam-Faculty of Social and Behavioural Sciences, International Institute of Social History (IISG), VU Amsterdam-Faculty of Behavioural and Movement Sciences, Maastricht University-Faculty of Science and Engineering, Centerdata, Utrecht University-Faculty of Social Sciences, Netherlands eScience Center (NLeSC), and VU Amsterdam-Faculty of Social Sciences. VU Amsterdam-Faculty of Social Sciences this year took over task 4.5 – Benchmarking from NLeSC.

Key performance indicators for the infrastructure have been set out by the Coordination Team and consulted across ODISSEI.

Table 1 - Key Performance Indicators

Indicator	Target	Current
Development		
Participation of all social science and economics faculties	All social science and economics faculties to be full ODISSEI members by 2025	All social science faculties are members. 6 of 15 Economics faculties still have to sign up.
Participation in European projects	Active participation in at least two European Level projects by 2025	New work programme published in summer 2021. Submissions in 2021-2022.
International infrastructure collaborations	Formal collaboration with similar initiatives in UK, US, FR, and DE	Initial contact has been made with discussion of formalization
Data Access & Analysis		
Percentage of researchers at ODISSEI member organisations submitting a proposal	Receive project proposals from 10% of researchers at ODISSEI member organisations	Currently approximately 7% of researchers have submitted
Percentage of researchers at ODISSEI member organisations being granted a project	Provide access to 5% of researchers at ODISSEI member organisations by 2025	Currently 1% of researchers have received a grant
Number of unique visitors to the ODISSEI Portal	No current target set	None as Portal is still in development
Number of OSSC Projects per year	7 per year	6 per year
Number of projects spanning more than 2 service providers	No current target set	1 project using multiple elements with 3 further projects starting by the end of 2021
Financial		
Further successful funding applications	Participation in a successful 2022 Roadmap Application for SSH	Preparations of 2022 Roadmap proposal under way
Total amount committed by member organisations	By 2025, to receive continuation of existing commitments to 2029 as a minimum	Current contributions are perpetual but no commitments until 2029
Training & Education		
Number of attendees at training events and workshops	600 unique attendees at events per year	404 for 2020-2021
Number of projects supported by Social Data Analytics Team (SoDa)	No current target set	4 projects in 2020-2021
Science & Technology		
Number of scientific papers describing the infrastructure	3 per year by 2025	2 in 2020-2021
Number of peer-reviewed publications derived from	30 per year by 2025	8 in 2020-2021

ODISSEI supported research projects

Number of citations received for publications derived from ODISSEI supported research projects *No current target set* *23 in 2020-2021*

Social and Economic Impact

Number of datasets contributed by non-academic organizations *Five datasets from industry partners contributed by 2025* *2*

Number of government agencies participating as member organisations *No current target set* *5*

Number of website visits *No current target set* *9,200 in 2020-2021*

Press mentions in the Netherlands *No current target set* *Monitoring not yet operational*

Communication

Number of social media (e.g. Twitter, LinkedIn) subscribers *No current target set* *655*

Number of newsletter subscribers *Total of 1,000 by 2025* *596*

Attracting New Talent

Number of international scientists recruited by ODISSEI *No current target set* *Monitoring not yet operational*

Number of international grants using ODISSEI (e.g. MCSA, ERC etc) *No current target set* *None*

5 Roadmap Budget

In the financial years 2020-2021 through 2023-2024, ODISSEI will execute the Roadmap project with the budget as earlier approved by the Supervisory Board and NWO. A full breakdown and justification of this budget is available in the ODISSEI Roadmap proposal which is [available on the ODISSEI website](#). An overview, with slight movements between the financial years and between tasks at EUR, is given in Table 4.

The NWO Roadmap grant is **€ 9,300,000**. The other funding streams are earlier, yet unspent, NWO grants (**€ 1,100,000**), member contributions (**€ 3,180,000**) and ODISSEI's own cash reserve (**€ 362,000**). This adds up to the budget for the entire project of **€ 13,942,000**, which is spent more or less evenly over the four financial years.

Table 3 – Agreed upon Roadmap Budget for 2020-2024

	(in k€)	2020-2021	2021-2022	2022-2023	2023-2024 ²	Total Roadmap
Data Facility		1.191	1.317	1.029	1.478	5.015
1.1 Microdata		394	360	444	690	1.888
1.2 Data products		40	45	62	87	234
1.3 ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer		615	638	246	279	1.779
1.4 Portal		142	274	276	422	1.114
Observatory		455	1.264	925	223	2.867
2.1 Data collection		323	1.059	698	45	2.125
2.2 Media Content Analysis Lab		60	62	63	86	270
2.3 Historical Sample of the Netherlands		71	72	92	-	236
2.4 Netherlands Twin Register		-	71	72	92	236
Laboratory		493	739	294	841	2.367
3.1 Distributed learning		66	89	-	-	155
3.2 Automatic linking		71	72	74	101	318
3.3 Survey innovations		260	520	220	740	1.740
3.4 Mass experiments		19	58	-	-	77
3.5 Citizen science		77	-	-	-	77
Hub		503	935	873	1.380	3.692
4.1 Community management		230	455	451	941	2.078
4.2 Education		10	40	41	85	176
4.3 ODISSEI Social Analytics Team		97	224	168	319	808
4.4 eScience grants		166	192	192	-	550
4.5 Benchmarking platform		-	23	22	35	80
		2.642	4.256	3.121	3.922	13.942

² This period of the Roadmap project covers 1.5 year.

6 Financial Results 2020-2021

An overview of the financial results for 2020-2021 is given in Table 4.

ODISSEI is on a firm financial footing. In the financial year 2020-2021, NWO transferred the first batch (**€ 2,524,000**) of the € 9,300,000 Roadmap grant. 42 member organisations and one observer member contributed a total of **€ 680,000**. Almost all have reaffirmed their commitment until 2024.

In addition, **NWO** has provided **€ 550,000** for ODISSEI's **core budget**. This contribution has been affirmed until the financial year 2021-2022, when it will cease to be given.

ODISSEI started the financial year with a **cash reserve** of € 380,000, which increased to **€ 2,211,000**. Most cash reserves will be spent over the course of the Roadmap project and the current surplus is in line with the Roadmap Project budget agreed in 2020.

Almost all tasks in the Roadmap project started in this financial year. As a result, expenses grew from € 1.4 million in the previous year to € 1.9 million. This is still less than the budgeted €2.6 million, caused by the deferred start-ups of tasks due the corona crisis and deferral of OSSC developments until the launch of the new national supercomputer Snellius in autumn 2021. The Management Board expects that spending will be back in line with initial projections within the 2021-2022 financial year. All tasks will finish within budget and on time and therefore the Management Board expects no underspending over the course of the Roadmap project.

Table 4 - Income and Expenditure 2016-2017 to 2020-2021

	(in k€)	2016-2017	2017-2018	2018-2019	2019-2020	Actual 2020-2021	Planned 2020-2021	+/-
Income		525	1.040	1.587	1.175	3.754	3.739	15
NWO contribution		400	550	550	550	550	550	-
NWO Bridge grant				487				
NWO Roadmap grant						2.524	2.524	-
Member organisations		125	490	550	625	680	665	15
Expenses		287	852	1.372	1.436	1.923	2.642	719
Data Facility			35	603	464	753	1.191	438
1.1 Microdata			35	278	296	330	394	64
1.2 Use cases						-	40	40
1.3 ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer				325	85	216	615	399
1.4 Portal					83	207	142	-65
Observatory		280	799	30	81	365	455	89
2.1 Data collection		280	799	30	81	334	323	-10
<i>Data scouts</i>						-	71	71
<i>ESS National Coordinator</i>					45	45	45	-
<i>EVS Fieldwork</i>			160				-	-
<i>NKO Fieldwork</i>			170			177	177	-
<i>SHARE fieldwork</i>		280	439			75	-	-75
<i>LIS contribution</i>			30	30	36	36	30	-6
2.2 Media Content Analysis Lab						10	60	50
2.3 Historical Sample of NL						21	71	50
2.4 Netherlands Twin Register						-	-	-
Laboratory				640	660	319	493	174
3.1 Distributed Analytics						74	66	-7
3.2 Automatic Metadata						34	71	37
3.3 LISS				640	660	203	260	57
3.4 Mass Experiments						9	19	10
3.5 Citizen Science						-	77	77
Hub		7	18	99	231	486	503	17
4.1 Community Management		7	18	99	231	323	230	-93
4.2 Education							10	10
4.3 SoDa						161	97	-64
4.4 Pathfinder grants						2	166	164
4.5 Benchmarks						-	-	-
Result (income minus expenses)		238	188	215	-261	1.831		
Cash reserve (accumulated result)		238	426	641	380	2.211		

Annex 1 – Microdata Access Discount

Table 5 - Microdata Access Discount Projects

Applicant or Administrator ³	Affiliation	Project Title
Adriaan Kalwij	UU-REBO	Socioeconomic status, health and the role of the welfare state
Alexandros Dimitropoulos	PBL	Evaluatie en voorspelling autokeuze- en mobiliteitsgedrag
Ana Santos	EUR-ESE	Job loss and Wealth
Anet Weterings	PBL	De concurrentiepositie van regio's en regionale arbeidsmobiliteit
Anja Dirkwager	NSCR	Zorggebruik en gezondheidsproblemen gedetineerden voor en na detentie
Anke Ramakers	UL-Law	In a job, out of trouble?
Anne Gielen	EUR-ESE	Spill-over effects of government policies
Anne Gielen	EUR-ESE	Intergenerational effects of economic shocks
Anne Teirlinck	RIVM	Direct measurement of Respiratory Syncytial Virus (RSV) healthcare burden in young children
Anne-Fleur Roos	EUR-ESHM	Prestaties Nederlandse ziekenhuizen
Annemarie Gielen	EUR-ESE	Spill-over effects of governments policies
Annemiek Val	UvA-FMG	De predictieve validiteit van de ARIJ-risicotaxatie
Annemiek Val	UvA-FMG	Verbetering vroegsignalering in de jeugdgezondheidszorg
Anne-Rigt Poortman	UU-FSW	Gezinsdiversiteit na scheiding
Anouk Hölsgens	UM-SBE	The influence of workers skills and ict investment on firm's innovative performance
Anouk Hölsgens	UM-SBE	Publicatie bestand EBB 2002
Anouk Hölsgens	UM-SBE	Open innovation, networks, and firm performance
Anouk Hölsgens	UM-SBE	Jongeren Not in Employment, Education or Training (NEET) gedurende de school-naar-werk transitie in Nederland
Anouk Hölsgens	UM-SBE	De voorspellende waarde van toetsen en schooladviezen op korte en lange termijn
Antonie Knigge	UU-FSW	Gene-environment interplay in education: the impact of school quality and tracking
Bas van der Klaauw	VU-SBE	School and study choice: Matching and return
Bas van der Klaauw	VU-SBE	Evaluatie loting scholen
Bastian Ravesteijn	EUR-ESE	The social returns to mental health care: Evidence from a Dutch payment reform
Bastian Ravesteijn	EUR-ESE	Human capital development in the Netherlands
Bastian Ravesteijn	EUR-ESE	Alternative work arrangements in the Netherlands
Boram Kim	TUD-ABE	Measuring multi-dimensional housing disadvantages
Carla Haelermans	UM-SBE	Het effect van ouderbetrokkenheid via een app op huiswerkgedrag en leerprestaties
Chris van Klaveren	VU-FGB	Onderwijsstromen
Chris van Klaveren	VU-FGB	Maatschappelijke positie mensen met een beperking in Nederland
Christianne van Domburg Scipio Chang	UvA-FMG	Ruimtelijke en sociale dynamiek en buurteffecten
Daniel Karpati	TiU-TISEM	Adverse health effects of financial distress: The moderating role of family firms
Diane Conforius	UvA-FMG	Arbeidsmarktpositie allochtonen ten zuiden Sahara

³ For MAD applications, the named individual is often the data manager and not the researcher

Dirk Brounen	TiU-TiSEM	Energy efficiency in the housing market
Dorret Boomsma	VU-FGB	Heritability of twinning in the Netherlands
Eric Smit	RIVM	Healthy districts: Gezondheidseffecten van de wijkenaanpak
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Kansrijk onderwijsbeleid
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Indicaties en gebruik van langdurige zorg
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Structurele veranderingen op de arbeidsmarkt
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Woonoorden van Molukkers
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Reikwijdte van agglomeratie-effecten in Nederland
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Evaluatie scholingsaftrek
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	De economische impact van huizenprijsschokken op zelfstandige ondernemers
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Vermogens en schulden van Nederlandse huishoudens
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Financiële regelingen en arbeidsmarktgedrag
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Koplopers en volgers
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Gemeentelijk Sociaal Domein
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Vernieuwing eigen risico model
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Financieringsvraagstukken bedrijfsleven
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Ongelijkheid
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Comparative advantage In the Netherlands
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Regionale verschillen in onderwijsuitkomsten
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Buitenlandse vermogens en de inkeerregeling
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Inkomens- en remgeldeffecten bij het verplicht eigen risico
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Patiëntpopulatie in academische ziekenhuizen
Esther Hermans-Spijker	TiU-TiSEM	Pension contributions
Eva Jaspers	UU-FSW	De rol van sociaal kapitaal in de arbeidsmarktongelijkheid tussen mensen met en zonder migratieachtergrond
Evert Meijers	TUD-ABE	MultipliCity
Gülbike Mirzaoglu	TiU-TiSEM	The effect and prevalence of crime prevention measures: shutter adoption in the Netherlands
Hadewijch van Delft	VU-SBE	Pendelafstanden
Hadewijch van Delft	VU-SBE	Economic consequences of migration
Hadewijch van Delft	VU-SBE	The attractors of Dutch cities
Hadewijch van Delft	VU-SBE	Urban consumers
Hadewijch van Delft	VU-SBE	Regionale en stedelijke economische ontwikkeling
Hadewijch van Delft	VU-SBE	Housing prices
Hadewijch van Delft	VU-SBE	Innovation and performance of workers, firms and regions
Hans Uytenhout	NIDI	Hongerwinter-project
Hans van Kippersluis	EUR-ESE	Income, health, and work across the life cycle II
Hendrik Letterie	VU-SBE	Hervormingen in de Nederlandse markt voor de langdurige zorg: De waarde van meer keuze schatten
Hendrik Vrijburg	UL-Law	An empirical and applied general equilibrium analysis of capital income taxation in the Netherlands
Hilde Wermink	UL-Law	Life after release: Understanding effects of imprisonment on the further life-course
Inge Wichgers	RUG	Wat is de relatie tussen profiel- en sectorkeuze en schoolkenmerken van het voortgezet onderwijs
Iltai Shacham	TiU-TiSEM	Characterizing firm growth across towns

Jannine Van de Maat	SCP	Overall monitor sociaal domein
Jannine Van de Maat	SCP	Verdiepende studie integratie
Jannine Van de Maat	SCP	Eindevaluatie Participatiewet
Jannine Van de Maat	SCP	Engelstalig HO
Jeanne Gubbels	UvA-FMG	Langetermijneffect onderzoek interventies voor kindermishandeling en predictieve validiteit LIJ voor toekomstige zorgwekkende opgroei- en opvoedingssituaties.
Jose Carreno	TiU-TISEM	The effects of rising contractual flexibility on the dynamics of hiring practices, wages, and real outcomes.
Kars van Oosterhout	UM-SBE	Geographical accessibility and educational choices
Kim Janssens	TiU-TSB	Op zoek naar werk: Wat werkt voor wie en waarom?
Konstantin Sommer	UvA-FEB	The effects of the European carbon trading system and its transition towards an auction based system. Evidence from Dutch microdata.
Lisanne Vonk	UM-SBE	Gezonde school
Lkhagvaa Erdenesuren	TiU-TISEM	Ageing and retirement in the Netherlands
Maarten Van Ham and Van Dorst	TUD-ABE	Neighbourhood effects, neighbourhood change and segregation
Maarten Van Ham and Van Dorst	TUD-ABE	StatusCities: Migrant legal STATUS diversity and diversity dynamics in CITIES
Maarten Lindeboom	VU-SBE	Work health
Maarten Lindeboom	VU-SBE	Patiëntvoorkeuren voor ziekenhuiszorg
Marco Helbich	UU-GEO	NEEDS
Marieke Knoef	UL-Law	Welfare reforms and criminal behaviour
Marieke Knoef	UL-Law	Inkomen, vermogen en ouderdagsvoorzieningen van Nederlandse huishoudens
Martijn Smit	VU-SBE	Knowledge spillovers, absorptive capacity and the Dutch CIS
Martijn Hendriks	EUR-ESE	De invloed van asielzoekerscentra op het gelukt van omwonenden
Martin Salm	TiU-TISEM	Effect of internal migration on regional inequalities in health and healthcare expenditures in the Netherlands
Mirjam Knol	RIVM	Non-specific effects of vaccination
Monique Dijks	RUG-FGMW	De profielkeuze verklaard vanuit de Theory of Planned Behaviour
Narly Dwarkasing	EUR-ESE	ECB policy and Dutch households
Olivier Marie	EUR-ESE	The power of the Dutch pill
Olivier Marie	EUR-ESE	Held back by discrimination?
Pascal Achard	TiU-TISEM	The transitional dynamics of cultural integration
Pascal Beckers	RU-FMW	The relation between mental health and labour market participation of Syrian refugees
Patricia Rowel	SCP	Vershil in Nederland 2019-SCR 2021
Patricia Rowel	SCP	Vershil in Nederland 2014
Patricia Rowel	SCP	De woonomgeving als onze binding
Pierre Koning	UL-Law	Leiden versoberingen in arbeidsongeschiktheidsregelingen tot meer werk?
Pierre Koning	VU-SBE	Onderzoek naar de relatie tussen werk, gezondheid en arbeidsongeschiktheidsuitkeringen
Pieter Bakx	EUR-ESHM	Financial and health risks: Household decisions and government interventions
Pim Kastelein	UvA-FEB	Pension funding, housing wealth and macroeconomic demand
Rafiq Friperon	VU-SBE	Segregatie en onderwijsuitkomsten
Raymond Montizaan	UM-SBE	Het causale effect van een geneeskundeopleiding op psychische gezondheid
Renata Rabovic	TiU-TISEM	Teacher discretion in tracking assessments

Ron Diris	UM-SBE	De invloed van omgevingsfactoren en uitkomsten in primair en voortgezet onderwijs op de latere uitkomsten van leerlingen in Limburg
Ron Diris	UU-REBO	Mobiliteit op de Nederlandse arbeidsmarkt
Ruben van Gaalen	UvA-FMG	Sociale ongelijkheid om veranderingen in levenslopen
Sabien Dobbelaere	VU-SBE	Interaction between innovation and firm dynamics
Sander Steijn	SCP	Cohortstudie statushouders
Sander Steijn	SCP	Gebruik en niet-gebruik voorzieningen sociaal domein
Sander Steijn	SCP	Differentiatie in het hoger onderwijs
Shuai Chen	EUR-ESE	Lagged duration dependent survival analysis on the same-sex partnership formation and dissolution
Sjoerd Van Bakkum	EUR-ESE	ECB collateral eligibility and bank risk-taking
Sofija Pajic	UvA-FEB	LeadHealth
Steve van de Weijer	NSCR	Effecten van individuele en intergenerationele levensgebeurtenissen op crimineel gedrag
Susan Hahné	RIVM	Infectieziekten kengetallen ziekenhuizen (DHD)
Sytske Wiegersma	Nivel	Harmonization and integrative analysis of regional, national, and international cohorts on primary Sjogren's Syndrome
Thijs Bol	UvA-FMG	Organisations, occupation, and inequality
Tim Huijts	UM-SBE	Kinderen van PIAAC-respondenten
Tirza van der Straaten	UL-FSW	Schoolprestaties van dove en slechthorende kinderen in Nederland
Twan Huijtmans	UvA-FMG	The urban-rural divide in political attitudes
Willemijn Bezemer	EUR-ESSB	Op zoek naar vertrouwen: Begrijpen en verbeteren van jeugd/politie interacties in hedendaagse 'superdiverse' samenlevingen
Wim Bernasco	NSCR	Broken homes and crime
Wolter Hassink	UU-REBO	7672, Declining transaction prices in the Dutch housing market
Wolter Hassink	UU-REBO	The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the Dutch labour force
Zhiyong Wang	UU-GEO	Vitality data center
Zoltan Lippenyi	RUG-FGMW	Embedded transitions: Critical changes in individual and organizational lives and equity in society
Zsolt Csáfordi	EUR-ESE	Skill relatedness in cities and firms

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